

White Paper

Navigating Artificial Intelligence in Education: Pathways to Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion

An initiative of the Communities of Practices of AI and D&I at the Teaching Academy Groningen

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Executive summary

The recent ranking of 28th in *The World's Most International Universities 2025* demonstrates the University of Groningen's (UG) reputation for its high-quality, inclusive education serving diverse student populations and its commitment to fostering diversity and student success. However, recent developments threaten this progress through budget cuts that may lead to fewer educational opportunities, limited investment possibilities and reduced individual student support. Simultaneously, educators and students increasingly rely on Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools as convenient solutions amid limited resources, creating a critical intersection between digital technology adoption and Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) principles.

This white paper emerges from collaborative work between two Communities of Practice at the UG—one focused on DEI in teaching and learning, another on AI in Education. The paper's objective is to promote ethical selection, development, and use of digital tools grounded in DEI principles that support educational practice at the UG. It aims to guide broader community discussion on ethical AI integration while representing educator concerns and offering practical strategies.

Presented in the paper are three main calls for action. The first promotes ethical selection and use of digital tools through criteria for inclusivity, accessibility, and sustainability. Also proposed is exploring educational applications for AI literacy via transparency, responsive professional development, and aligned policies. The third recommendation is to involve the UG community in ethical AI integration discussions within a structure of educators and policymakers. These recommendations aim to address the urgent need to ensure that the necessary digital systems serve diverse populations equitably.

Introduction

In recent years, Dutch Higher Education has built a strong reputation for delivering high-quality education, fostering diversity in an inclusive teaching and learning environment. In March 2025, the University of Groningen (UG) was ranked 28th in *The World's Most International Universities 2025* by *Times Higher Education*, surpassing prestigious institutions such as MIT and Harvard (1). This recognition, among other indicators, reflects UG's continued investment in teaching and learning approaches that activate students and promote student success across diverse backgrounds. The aim of the UG is to be an inclusive academic environment that embraces and values diverse perspectives (2).

However, recent national political developments pose significant challenges. Proposed budget cuts may lead to more standardised educational approaches and a shift towards more extensified education, potentially reducing the attention and support available for individual students (3). Simultaneously, both students and educators are increasingly exploring the potential of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools and applications, especially when these offer convenient and efficient solutions in the face of limited resources (4). These trends are not without consequence: the growing reliance on digital tools will inevitably influence everyday practices also around Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI). From this DEI perspective, it is crucial that digital systems are designed and implemented to be equitable and inclusive, serving the needs of a diverse student and faculty population. Moreover, the intersection of AI and DEI is particularly relevant as digital tools can either reinforce existing barriers or help dismantle them, particularly for underrepresented groups (5).

Aim of this White Paper

At the Teaching Academy Groningen (TAG), two Communities of Practice (CoPs)—one focusing on DEI in teaching and learning and the other on AI in Education—have engaged in ongoing dialogue about the ethical concerns and potential opportunities associated with AI tools in education. These discussions led to the formation of a joint project group exploring these themes in more depth and articulating a shared perspective. The result of this process is this White Paper.

More specifically, **this white paper's objective** is to **promote ethical selection, development, and use of digital tools grounded in DEI principles** that align with and support educational practice at the University of Groningen. This includes policy that is guided by conscious consideration of DEI challenges regarding AI literacy, critical thinking, and academic integrity, as well as ensuring that educators possess key digital competences in order to engage with those challenges.

Therefore, the **aim of this white paper** is to serve as **a guide for broader discussion within the UG community** on the ethical integration of digital tools in education. It aims to represent the concerns and insights of UG educators, while also offering practical strategies and structural approaches for future decision-making around the ethical use of digital tools in teaching and learning—always with a strong emphasis on advancing DEI.

Overview and reader's guide

In the following sections, we will illustrate the DEI challenges in educational practice and key digital competences for teachers compiled in six areas. Teachers face these challenges in different ways and circumstances, depending on their disciplinary context, available support and designed teaching and learning environment present to them. Therefore, this white paper includes key competences based on the European Commission's DigCompEdu (6) and UNESCO's AI Competence Framework for Teachers (7) to inform on the intersection of teacher's agency in engaging with DEI challenges in digital education. Teachers operating in this intersection will need to be supported by institutional policy regarding either support of developing specific competences or providing a preselection in available digital tools for engaging with these challenges. The interconnections between DEI challenges and AI key competences will be discussed in relation to necessary policy development in the last sections of this White Paper. This section will function as recommendations to the UG community responding to both the objective and aim affirmed for this paper and stated in the previous section.

DEI challenges in digital education

This section summarises the **DEI challenges regarding AI literacy, critical thinking, and academic integrity**. Being aware of these challenges and continuously considering these in policy development is important for actively upholding DEI principles such as fairness, accessibility, and respect of the needs of all individuals, particularly those from marginalised and underrepresented groups (8- 27).

While some areas—such as the environmental impact—may be difficult to eliminate entirely, it is important to recognise the varying footprints of all technologies and digital tools, with some being more energy-efficient or environmentally conscious than others. In addition, environmental concerns might also raise the question whether a complex AI system is needed to solve a task in the first place, or if other less energy consuming alternatives could provide similar outcomes. Identifying these differences in all areas noted in Illustration 1 can guide educators to recognise which tools benefit their teaching and the learning of their students. Ideally, the resulting choices are guided by an institutional vision and aligned policies on DEI principles regarding ethical selection, use and development of digital tools.

Illustration 1: DEI challenges in digital education (More information on these DEI challenges are made available in the appendix A)

Digital key competences for educators

To address the challenges mentioned above, developing DEI-compatible digital competences are important. Grounded in the European Commission's DigCompEdu (6) and UNESCO's AI Competence Framework for Teachers (7), Illustration 2 **outlines an adapted version of digital key competences that educators should develop to meaningfully engage with digital tools through a DEI lens.**

These competences promote the ethical use of digital tools with the underlying intention to ensure inclusivity, enhanced accessibility, mitigated biases, and advanced social justice. Consequently, the aforementioned DEI challenges can be adequately acknowledged by developing these competences. By addressing DEI from a teaching perspective, the overview depicted in Illustration 2 supports AI literacy in educational practices and, therefore, the development of necessary competences of students in this area.

The competences can also function as a framework to support decision-making around the ethical selection and development of digital technologies as well as a guide for professional development of teachers. As this overview exemplifies, there are opportunities for ethical responsible education; however, this also involves conscious choices of resources and tools, where policy development and institutional structures should support and guide educators in making these choices.

Illustration 2: Digital Key Competences for Educators [adapted] (More information on these key dimensions, including examples of digital tools, are made available in Appendix B)

SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATIONS

As the objective of this white paper is to promote the ethical selection, development and use of digital tools, based on DEI principles and the aim is to stimulate wider discussion at the University of Groningen, recommendations are grouped into three calls for action.

The first recommendation is closely connected to the objective of this white paper and calls for ethical selection, development and use of digital tools. The second recommendation explores the wider implications for teaching and learning, and learning practice, regarding AI literacy for teachers. The third recommendation petitions for a policy-related structure and approach for this institution to sustainably support educational practice in the long term for the academic community.

I. Promote ethical selection, development, and use of digital tools

As higher education institutions increasingly adopt digital tools, it is crucial that these decisions are informed by DEI principles, such as fairness, accessibility and respect. Fairness also implies taking sustainability and long-term cost efficiency into account when selecting AI tools as these decisions indirectly affect the availability of other university resources. Whether open-source, custom-built or commercially licensed, decisions about AI tools must carefully balance short-term financial implications with long-term requirements such as maintenance, updates, build-up of expertise, adaptability, and strategic digital autonomy; such an emphasis aligns with a recent petition by several Dutch universities to promote digital autonomy away from big tech companies (28).

Accessibility is closely related to fairness. All staff should have access to recommended AI systems through existing digital environments such as Brightspace. Furthermore, students and staff must be made aware of tools that meet safety standards, particularly with regard to data protection. Clear and transparent information about AI tools that is aligned with university policies is crucial for safeguarding equal access for all stakeholders.

In practice, policies and decisions around AI implementation must actively ensure the representation of all students and staff, regardless of their background, and must reflect respect for their diverse needs. The real challenge lies in including the voices of underrepresented or marginalised groups and ensuring ongoing awareness of the biases that AI tools may perpetuate, which directly links to the need for AI literacy, explored in the next section.

In summary, the ethical selection and use of AI tools should be guided by clearly defined criteria in response to DEI challenges outlined in Illustration 1 (page 4). This white paper calls for the following criteria:

- **Inclusivity & Respect:** Representation of all stakeholders; awareness and prevention of bias (DEI challenge A & B)
- **Digital Safety & Accessibility:** Transparency; policy alignment; integration into existing educational systems (DEI challenge D & F)
- **Sustainability & Efficiency:** Consideration of both short-term and long-term implications of tool selection (DEI challenge C & E)

II. Explore educational applications for AI Literacy

From the perspective of educators, who are the main focus of this white paper, transparent information and accessible support are essential for the effective integration of AI tools into educational practice. This should be backed by consistent policy development at faculty and university level. In order to empower teachers to make informed choices about which tools to use and for what purpose, it is crucial to be transparent about the available tools and support systems. This information should also raise awareness of the DEI-related implications of AI use, including ethical concerns and potential bias as well as the role that AI can play in supporting inclusive education and students with specific needs. This is a broad area with many opportunities and challenges, and not all responsibilities can be taken on by teachers alone.

In order to realise the potential of AI in teaching and learning and to prepare students for an AI-informed world, it is crucial that professional development opportunities are made available to all educators. These opportunities should be responsive to their practical needs and diverse teaching contexts. Therefore, a variety of formats such as e-learning, individual consultation and training should be offered to develop key competences in teaching- and learning-related areas. Also proposed should be focus areas comprising disciplinary relevance, student needs and pedagogical methods.

This professionalisation process requires a shared vision and alignment across all organisational levels to ensure that support structures remain transparent, responsive and accessible. Policies and decisions regarding the usage of AI, particularly the selection of tools, should reflect a coherent approach at both the university and faculty levels. This approach should be grounded in the needs and experiences of the wider undergraduate academic community, and should encourage the sharing of ethical responsibilities.

In summary, exploring educational applications for AI literacy should include competence areas as illustrated (page 5) related to:

- **Transparency** around tools, policies, and DEI implications (educators professional competences area 1 & 2)
- **Responsive professional development** tailored to diverse teacher needs (educators pedagogical competencies area 3 & 4)
- **Aligned, consistent policies** that reflect educational practice and the educator's voice (facilitating learners' competences area 5 & 6)

III. Involve the UG community in discussions on ethical integration of AI

The aim of facilitating wider discussions about the ethical integration of digital tools and AI literacy in education within the UG community, including teachers, students and staff, is necessary for informed and unified decision-making. We suggest a bottom-up approach, grounded in educational practice, which has the potential to foster strong commitment within the UG community.

Therefore, the third recommendation is that a potential structure should include low-threshold consultation options, such as the CoPs on AI and DEI at the Teaching Academy

Groningen, which allow for two-way communication between educators and policymakers as demonstrated in Illustration 3.

Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs) could be collected and shared, and the corresponding resources (both internal and external to the UG) could be made accessible to the wider community. Signals emerging from these sessions, such as recurring issues, needs or policy-related concerns, can inform institutional policy development. To further support this approach, a clear framework for responsibility and follow-up should be established. Additionally, we propose establishing clear criteria that align with the aims of this white paper as well as a sounding board to discuss policy-related issues at a central level, further informing existing governance and decision-making structures, such as the Strategy department for Education and Students (SES) at University Services, the Council for Educational Quality (UCO), and the Education Council (Onderwijsberaad).

An inclusive approach of utilising UG’s varied perspectives would serve to inform both faculties and the university board of current educational developments and issues while providing a systematic basis for developing informed and responsive policies. The CoPs could then provide consultative expertise throughout this process, particularly when clarification or a deeper understanding is required. Consequently, the transparent flow of communication would also support the development of tailored educational support, transparency, and professional development offerings. Related internal and external resources could be curated and made accessible via the new Centre for Teaching and Learning (CTL) platform.

In summary, for involving the UG community in discussions on ethical integration of AI this white paper calls to:

- involve UG (teaching) staff in wider discussions over integrating AI through low-threshold consultation options, which could be set up in the CoPs on AI and DEI
- use FAQs and other resources to disseminate information to the wider community
- allow a two-way communication between educators and policymakers in order to make sure that policies support teaching and learning realities;
- utilise a sounding board for discussions at the central level to include UG entities as depicted in Illustration 3

Illustration 3: Potential Structure for involving UG community

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Appendix A : DEI challenges

The challenge of achieving DEI in the field of AI stems from the biases and discriminatory patterns encoded in training data, which reflect societal inequities, but it is compounded by other challenges as well. Key challenges on a general level are outlined below.

1. Bias in data and algorithms

Because AI relies on data for training and decision-making, it reflects societal biases, leading to the misclassification and marginalisation of certain groups. AI detectors often misclassify non-native English writing as AI-generated, disadvantaging these students, while predictive algorithms disproportionately label Black and Latinx students as "high risk" or likely to fail (8- 9). These biases, embedded in data and design, create feedback loops that reinforce discrimination and limit opportunities.

2. Accessibility issues

Disparities in infrastructure, language support, and affordability of AI technologies often limit marginalised communities' access to AI-driven tools and services, restricting their contributions to information datasets. Research reveals a critical gap in AI accessibility, with a focus on visual impairments while neglecting other disabilities (10- 11). A more comprehensive approach to AI accessibility is needed to prevent exclusion and discrimination.

3. Commercialisation and colonialist practices in AI development

The profit-driven models dominating AI development frequently sideline DEI by prioritising marketability over fairness. The focus on profit over education favors efficiency and revenue generation over equitable access. In turn, training Large Language Models often involves the exploitation of labor from economically disadvantaged regions or marginalised groups (12- 18). Such commercial and exploitative practices echo historical patterns of resource extraction, reinforcing global inequalities and preventing marginalised groups from meaningfully participating in or benefiting from the AI economy.

4. Datafication and data privacy concerns

Datafication in education, fueled by digital technologies and advanced analytics, poses a significant threat to DEI. The increasing quantification of learning deprioritised creativity, critical thinking, and social interaction, reinforcing biases through algorithmic decision-making (19- 22). Meanwhile, opaque student data collection and sharing heighten privacy risks. Moreover, the commercialisation of education transforms user interactions into

marketable assets, enabling surveillance and profiling that disproportionately impact marginalised students. As a result, algorithmic models often disadvantage those who deviate from predefined learning patterns, while commercial digital tools reflect and amplify developer biases, exacerbating educational inequalities.

Also there is a concrete risk that users share sensitive information with the system that makes them vulnerable, especially if they are somehow associated with marginalized communities - it is quite difficult to predict how this data will or will not be used in the future at this point in time, so better to try to find ways (e.g. paid subscriptions) that would limit that impact.

5. Environmental impact of AI

The environmental impact of AI extends beyond energy use to the mining of rare minerals essential for hardware and the improper disposal of electronic waste. Mining operations, often conducted in regions with weak environmental regulations, result in severe ecological damage, including deforestation and water contamination. Meanwhile, electronic waste disposal exposes communities to toxic substances, posing serious health risks (23). These practices disproportionately affect low-income and marginalised regions, exacerbating global inequities as these communities bear the environmental and social costs of AI development.

6. Ethical and legal ambiguities

Many jurisdictions lack comprehensive policies addressing ethical AI usage, leading to inconsistent practices (24- 27). Already existing regulations are often unevenly and limitedly enforced, leaving underrepresented groups vulnerable to harm.

Appendix B: Digital key competencies

Grounded in the European Commission's DigCompEdu (6) and Unesco's AI Competence Framework for Teachers (7), the proposed framework **outlines key competences that educators can develop to meaningfully engage with AI through a DEI lens and supports the ethical integration of digital tools and AI literacy.**

To provide a clearer understanding of how AI can support ethical and inclusive education, this appendix includes more information on key dimensions and a selection of digital tools that exemplify the functionalities described in this framework. However, these tools serve only as examples of how AI-driven functionalities can contribute to DEI principles; they are not endorsements of the tools themselves as inherently equitable or bias-free. Rather, this selection helps stakeholders envision concrete use cases while maintaining a critical perspective on the ethical implications of AI integration in education.

Area 1: Professional Engagement with a DEI focus

1.1 Organisational Communication with AI

- Enhances inclusivity and accessibility in interactions with students, colleagues, and other stakeholders
- Facilitates equal participation
- Enables clearer, more inclusive communication across linguistic and ability differences

1.2 Professional Collaboration with AI

- Allows sharing of knowledge, experiences, and pedagogical practices that integrate DEI and human-centered principles
- Facilitates interdisciplinary projects
- Fosters innovation in lesson design
- Addresses global and local DEI challenges
- Examples of current digital tools:
 - Notion AI – Supports multilingual communication
 - Miro – Enables real-time collaborative brainstorming
 - Curipod – Assists with idea generation and interactive presentations
 - Edvo AI – Facilitates adaptive learning and research assistance
 - Trello – Enhances workflow management and team communication

1.3 Reflective Practice with AI

- Enables educators to critically assess and refine pedagogical approaches with a focus on DEI and human-centered principles
- Provides analytics on teaching effectiveness, highlighting areas for improvement in instructional design, student engagement, and inclusivity
- Facilitates collaborative reflection by analysing lesson plans, assessments, and classroom interactions
- Offers targeted suggestions for more equitable teaching practices

- Examines educational algorithms for potential biases in grading, content delivery, and accessibility
- Fosters more inclusive learning environments.
- Examples of current digital tools:
 - AI Fairness 360 – Bias detection tool that analyses educational algorithms for fairness in grading, content delivery, and accessibility
 - Google What If – Interactive tool for exploring AI models and assessing potential biases in decision-making processes
 - Socrative – AI-enhanced platform for formative assessment and student engagement analytics
 - Kahoot! – Gamified learning and assessment tool that provides insights into student participation and understanding
 - Learning Analytics (integrated in Brightspace) – AI-driven analytics tools for evaluating student engagement

1.4 Digital Continuous Professional Development with AI

- Deepens educators' understanding of DEI in AI-augmented education
- Helps identify and synthesise case studies exploring the intersection of AI, education, and DEI
- Enables educators to assess trends, refine teaching practices, and ensure inclusive, human-centered AI integration
- Personalised professional development: courses, webinars, and resources based on educators' teaching history, interests, and student feedback
- Provides targeted suggestions for inclusive teaching strategies, fostering continuous growth in DEI-focused pedagogy
- Examples of current digital tools:
 - Semantic Scholar, ResearchRabbit, Elicit, Perplexity, Consensus – Helps educators find evidence-based research
 - Coursera – Offers AI-powered personalised course recommendations for professional development
 - LinkedIn Learning – Provides tailored learning pathways based on educators' interests and needs

Area 2: Digital Resources with a DEI Focus

2.1 Selecting Digital Resources for DEI with AI

- Selects digital resources that align with DEI principles by assisting in accessibility audits, bias detection, and representation analysis.
- Assesses compliance with Web Content Accessibility Guidelines, flag exclusionary language or stereotypes, and evaluate diversity in visual content
- Recommends DEI-aligned resources, vetted libraries, and personalised suggestions based on educators' needs, ensuring equitable and inclusive learning materials
- Examples of current digital tools:
 - Blackboard Ally – Assesses digital content for accessibility compliance and provides alternative formats
 - Otter.ai – AI-powered transcription tool that enhances accessibility by generating real-time captions and transcripts

2.2 Creating and Modifying Digital Resources for Inclusivity with AI

- Enhances accessibility and adaptability
- Ensures resources meet accessibility standards
- Accommodate diverse learner needs
- Adapts content for multilingual classrooms, fostering inclusivity in diverse learning environments
- Examples of current digital tools:
 - Canva – AI-powered design tool
 - Adobe Express – AI-assisted content creation platform with accessibility features
 - Read&Write – Text-to-speech and literacy support tool that enhances accessibility
 - Otter.ai – AI-powered speech-to-text tool for transcription and note-taking
 - DeepL – AI-driven translation tool that supports multilingual learning environments

2.3 Managing, Protecting, Sharing Digital Resources Responsibly with AI

- Ensures data privacy and security
- Safeguards sensitive student data, enabling educators to share resources while upholding ethical and legal standards for data protection
- Examples of current digital tools:
 - ARX Data Anonymisation – AI-powered tool for anonymising sensitive student data

Area 3: Teaching and Learning with a DEI Focus

3.1 Orchestrating Inclusive Digital Instruction with AI

- Adapts learning experiences to diverse student needs
- Personalised instruction based on individual backgrounds and learning profiles
- Enhances engagement and makes complex concepts more accessible.
- Examples of current digital tools:
 - Labster – AI-driven simulations that enhance engagement and make complex scientific concepts more accessible
 - Century Tech – Adaptive AI platform that personalises instruction based on individual learning profiles

3.2 Enhancing Targeted and Inclusive Support with AI

- Provides real-time assistance and identifying students who may need additional help
- Addresses student queries with multilingual and accessibility features
- Detects at-risk students, enabling proactive and personalised interventions

3.3 Teamwork and Communication with AI

- Enhances teamwork and communication in group settings
- Supports creative problem-solving

- Helps assess group dynamics, ensuring all voices are heard and addressing participation imbalances

3.4 Empowering Learners for Self-Direction with AI

- Helps students plan, monitor, and reflect on their progress
- Personalised learning pathways
- Highlights achievements and areas for growth
- Guides students in documenting and analysing their learning journey

Area 4: Assessment with a DEI Focus

4.1 Diversifying Inclusive Assessment with AI

- Offers diverse and equitable evaluation methods
- Accommodates different learning styles
- Provides immediate feedback while minimising bias through continuous calibration
- Assesses oral presentations and collaborative discussions
- Examples of current digital tools:
 - Gradescope – AI-assisted grading platform that provides immediate feedback
 - ExamSoft – AI-powered assessment tool that accommodates different learning styles

4.2 Insights for Inclusive Learning with AI

- Provides data-driven insights into student experiences
- Identifies trends and gaps in performance across demographic groups
- Gauges student engagement and emotional responses, helping educators refine their approaches for greater inclusivity

4.3 Personalising Feedback with AI

- Provides targeted, timely insights that support diverse learning needs
- Delivers detailed, adaptive responses on student work
- Offers clear progress tracking for students
- Ensures accessibility and inclusivity across communication preferences

Area 5: Empowering Learners with a DEI focus with AI

- Trains educators to effectively use AI-driven accessibility tools, ensuring they recognise that accessibility is not one-size-fits-all
- Fosters transparency so teachers can assess AI tools, identify biases, and advocate for improvements
- Ensures equitable access to AI-powered learning by addressing barriers like access and digital literacy
- Supports educators in recognising and challenging algorithmic bias, critically evaluating AI-generated content, and advocating for fair, ethical AI implementation in education

Area 6: Facilitating Learners' AI Competence with a DEI Focus

6.1 Building Critical Awareness of AI-Driven Media with AI

- Helps learners evaluate AI-generated information with a focus on diversity and bias recognition
- Guides students in identifying credible, diverse sources, while comparing traditional sources with AI-generated summaries can help uncover potential omissions or biases

6.2 Fostering Inclusive AI-Mediated Engagement with AI

- Enables learners to collaborate effectively and equitably using AI-driven tools
- Ensures all voices are heard in collaborative discussions

6.3 Promoting Ethical AI Creativity and Expression with AI

- Guides learners in responsible digital content creation while fostering awareness of copyright, licensing, and ethical AI use
- Helps learners produce culturally and socially inclusive media, while discussions on AI-generated content can encourage critical reflection on intellectual property, authorship, and cultural appropriation

6.4 Encouraging Ethical AI Practices for Well-being with AI

- Promotes responsible and ethical engagement with digital technologies
- Offers initial mental health screenings
- Connects students to each other based on learning needs/interests and hobbies
- Connects students to resources, and provide timely support
- Frees up educators' time for meaningful student interactions
- Helps identify students in need of academic or personal support, enabling early intervention
- Offer mindfulness exercises and stress management tools to foster overall well-being

6.5 Applying AI Competence to Address Real-World Challenges with AI

- Empowers learners to apply their knowledge ethically and creatively to real-world challenges, fostering problem-solving and innovation in diverse contexts
- Supports learners in designing solutions for social or environmental issues
- Encourages collaborative approaches to technical problem-solving
- Helps learners explore equitable solutions to community challenges, and critical analysis of AI decision-making processes, such as bias in hiring algorithms, can inspire discussions on responsible AI interventions
- Examples of current digital tools:
 - WolframAlpha – AI-powered computational engine for problem-solving and data analysis
 - Google Colab – Collaborative coding environment for developing and testing AI models
 - CodeT5 – AI-powered code generation and debugging tool
 - NetLogo – Simulation software for modeling complex social and environmental systems
 - Simulink – AI-driven simulation and modeling tool for engineering and real-world system analysis